

**Revision of the taxonomic structure of
Tetrops gilvipes (Faldermann, 1837)
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: Three new subspecies are described: *Tetrops gilvipes efetovi* ssp. n. from Crimea on the base of differently colored specimens with black and yellow elytra; *T. g. murzini* ssp. n. from Kopet-Dag Ridge (Turkmenia) and Talysh (Azerbaijan) on the base of specimens with black elytra; *T. g. adelbaueri* ssp. n. from West Europe (type locality: Závist, Czechia) on the base of specimens with yellow elytra; *Tetrops gilvipes niger* Kraatz, 1859 is regarded as a subspecies distributed in Italy and France.

The taxonomic position of *T. gilvipes* can not be regarded as generally accepted (Sama, 2002). For example: according to Plavilstshikov (1932) and Villiers (1967) it is a subspecies of *T. praeusta* (Linnaeus, 1758); according to Winkler (1929), Kaszab (1971) and Sama (1988) it is a synonym of *T. praeusta* – black form; according to Heyrovský (1955) *T. gilvipes* includes *T. starkii* Chevrolat, 1859 as a synonym; according to Bense (1995), Villiers (1978) and Berger (2012) it includes *T. niger* Kraatz, 1859 as a synonym and so on. The separation of *T. praeusta* and *T. gilvipes* was shown by Starzyk & Lessaer (1978). Besides larvae *T. gilvipes* can be easily differed (Danilevsky, Miroshnikov, 1985) from *T. praeusta* by numerous fine spiculae which cover abdominal segments, while in *T. praeusta* abdominal spiculae are big and scattered.

Several abbreviations used in the text:

AN - collection of A. Napolov, Riga (Latvia)

GS - collection of G. Sama, Cesena (Italy).

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow (Russia)

ML - collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow (Russia)

SM - collection of S. Murzin, Moscow (Russia)

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MPSU - Moscow Pedagogical State University, Moscow (Russia)
ZIN - Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, Sankt-Petersburg (Russia)
ZMM - Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow (Russia)

***Tetrops gilvipes* (Faldermann, 1837)**

(Figs 1-8)

Anaetia gilvipes Faldermann, 1837: 290 - "Fauna entomologica transcaucasica"

Tetrops nigra Kraatz, 1859: 57 - „Sardinien“; Holzschuh, 1981: 82;

Polyopsia gilvipes, Mulsant, 1862: 347 (?+ var. *nigra* Kr., ?+ var. *muehlfeldi* Muls.)
– “le Caucase, etc.”.

Polyopsia gilvipes var. *muehlfeldi* Mulsant, 1862: 348 – “dans les Alpes cottiennes”

Tetrops gilvipes, Ganglbauer 1882: 586, part. – “Caucasus”; Ogloblin, 1948: 471 – Ciscaucasia, Crimea; Plavilstshikov, 1948: 200, part. - North Armenia, Sevan, Alagez; 1955: 546, part. - Caucasus, Transcaucasus, Turcmenia (Kopet-Dag); Shmidt, 1958: 60 (= *nigra* Kr.), part. – “Westibirien (Gebler), Sibirien: Werchne Udinsk (Mandl), Kaspigebiet: Liryk; Lenkoran, “Circassia”, Georgien (Achalzich), Kaukasus (Terekgebiet, Borshom, Araxestal), Krim (Simferopol), “Tauria merid.”, Slovaei (Banska, Bystrica, Hermanee, Hronska Breznica), Koralpe (v. Demelt), Millstadt, leg. Sattler 15.6.92 (Senckenberg-Museum); Friaul: Somplago (v. Demelt), Avezzano, Lazio (Monte Cavo), Italia centr.: Camerata Nuova, Sardinien, Cottische Alpen (Fenestrelle), Piemont, St.Bernhard (Stierlin), Alpes maritimes (Berthemont, Moulinet), St.Martin Vésubie, Drôme: Romans und Montélimar (Xambeu nach Planet); Pyrenäen (4 Expl. In coll. Koltze, Fundort erscheint mir sehr fraglich); Breuning, 1965: 651 (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) – “S. Germany, Austria”); Plavilstshikov, 1965: 419 – Caucasus, Crimea; Murzin, 1977: 302 - Caucasus, Kopetdag; Villiers, 1978: 503 (= *nigra* Kraatz, 1859 = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) - “Europe méridionle, Caucase”; Starzyk & Lessaer, 1978: 35-45; Holzschuh, 1981: 81, part. (“türkisch- und russisch Armenien, Kaukasus, Talysch, Elburz und Kopet Dag”); Berger, 1985: 169-171 – Alpes-Maritimes and Caucasus; Tsherepanov, 1985: 209, part; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 355, part. – Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kopet-Dag, West Europe; Tsherepanov, 1985: 209 (= *nigra* Kr.) – Middle Europe, Caucasus, Crimea, ?South Urals; Cocquempot, 1992: 201 – France; Sláma, 1998: 293, part.; Brustel, Berger & Cocquempot, 2002: 455 – “dans les Alpes-Maritimes et les Hautes-Alpes”, “Grèce”, “Caucase”; Kasatkin, 2005: 56 – Rostov Region of Russia; Bartenev, 2004: 39 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.) – from West Europe to Turkmenia; 2009: 339 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.)– from West Europe to Turkmenia; Özdikmen & Turgut, 2008: 623 (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi*

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- Muls.) – “Europe (?France, ?Italy, ?Romania, ?Hungary, ?Czechia, ?Slovakia, Crimea, S European Russia), Caucasus (Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan), Central Asia (Turkmenia, Iran”); Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 332 – Azerbajdzhan, Armenia, Georgia, South Russia, Ukraine, Iran, Turkmenia; Miroshnikov, 2011: 259 – Adygeya Region; Berger, 2012: 607 (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.)– “France, Italie, Croatie, Grèce occidentale, Turquie, Iran, Caucase”
- Tetrops praeusta* var. *nigra*, Ganglbauer 1882: 586, part.; Aurivillius, 1922: 573, part. – Gebirgsgegenden Süddeutschlands, Alpen; Planet, 1924: 327, part.; Winkler, 1929: 1226 – Alpes;
- Tetrops praeusta* var. *gilvipes*, Bogdanov-Katkov, 1917: 51 – “Ekaterinodar”; Aurivillius, 1922: 572, part. - Kaukasus;. Winkler, 1929: 1226, part. – Caucasus.
- Tetrops praeusta gilvipes*, Plavilstshikov, 1932: 195 - Caucasus; Villiers, 1967: 377, part. - “propre à la région caucasienne”, “Iran: Tariki Rud”);
- Tetrops praeusta*, Harde, 1966: 94, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.); Sláma, 1998: 293, part.
- Tetrops praeusta* ab *nigra*, Kaszab, 1971: 283, part.
- Tetrops praeustus*, Sama, 1988: 190, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.); 2002: 120, part. (= *nigra* Kr.); Bense, 1995: 469, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.); Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 36, part. (= *nigra* Kr.); Sláma, 2006: 38, part. (= *nigra* Kr.)
- Tetrops niger*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1994: 58, part.
- Tetrops praeusta praeusta*, Bartenev, 2004: 39 (= *nigra* Kr.), part. – from West Europe and North Africa to Kazakhstan; 2009: 336 (= *nigra* Kr.), part. – from West Europe and North Africa to Kazakhstan;
- Tetrops praeustus praeustus*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 333, part. (= *niger* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) Europe, Turkey, Syria, Transcaucasus, West and East Siberia, Kazakhstan, Mongolia; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 146, part. – Italy.

Type locality. Republic of Armenia. The type locality of *Tetrops gilvipes* (Faldermann, 1837) was not mentioned in the original description. Most of taxa described by F. Faldermann (1937) in “Fauna entomologica transcaucasica” seems to be connected with Iran or Azerbaijan. But one taxon is definitely connected with Armenia - *Dorcadion indutum* Faldermann, 1937 and several taxa with species absent in East Azerbaijan or Iran but very common in Armenia like *Mallosia scovitzi* Faldermann, 1937 or *Rhagium fasciculatum* Faldermann, 1937. So, for the stability of generally accepted sense of the name *Tetrops gilvipes*, it is necessary to accept Armenia as its type locality, though most of available specimens of the typical subspecies were collected in North-West Caucasus and Georgia. *T. gilvipes* was definitely recorded for Armenia

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(Plavilstshikov, 1948: 200 - Sevan, Alagez; Holzschuh, 1981: 81 – “russisch Armenien”).

Diagnosis. Body black with black or yellow elytra; frons distinctly punctated; antennae totally black, in males about as long as body or a little shorter, in females never reach elytral apices; 3rd antennal joint about as long as 1st; prothorax a little shorter than middle width, distinctly attenuated at base and widened near middle; pronotum shining, with fine scattered punctation; elytra densely punctated with dark or pale pubescence; legs usually totally yellow, or with partly dark middle and hind femora; last abdominal tergite in males rounded, in females – truncated; penis with sharp attenuated apex, parameres relatively wide and short (Starzyk & Lessaer, 1978: 40); body length in males: 3.0-4.9 mm, width: 0.9-1.4 mm; body length in females: 3.7-5.8 mm, width: 1.0 – 1.6 mm.

Genital structures (Starzyk & Lessaer, 1978: 40) is a good character to distinguish *T. gilvipes* from similar colored specimens of *T. praeusta*. In *T. praeusta* penis with shorter apex, parameres long and narrow (Starzyk & Lessaer, 1978: 40).

Distribution. From West Europe to Turkmenia, including Greece (Berger, 2000), Crimea, Caucasus with Transcaucasia, South Turkmenia (Kopet-Dag), North Iran and North-East Turkey (Artvin). The record of *T. gilvipes* for “Sibirien (Werchne Udinsk)” by Shmidt (1958) was definitely connected with *Tetrops mongolicus* Murzin, 1977. But the reasons of his record for West Siberia (with the reference to Gebler) are not clear, though it was supposed by Tsherepanov (1985) for South Urals.

The species consists of 5 subspecies. The nomenclature status of Greek population discovered by Berger (2000) rests uncertain.

***Tetrops gilvipes gilvipes* (Faldermann, 1837)**

Anaetia gilvipes Faldermann, 1837: 290 - “Fauna entomologica transcaucasica”

Polyopsia gilvipes, Mulsant, 1862: 347, part. (?+ var. *nigra* Kr., ?+ var. *muehlfeldi* Muls.) – “le Caucase, etc.”.

Tetrops gilvipes, Ganglbauer 1882b: 586 – “Caucasus”; Ogloblin, 1948: 471, part. – Ciscaucasia, Crimea; Plavilstshikov, 1948: 200 - North Armenia, Sevan, Alagez; 1955: 546, part. - Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkmenia (Kopet-Dag); 1965: 419, part. – Caucasus, Crimea; Murzin, 1977: 302, part. -

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- Caucasus, Kopetdag; Villiers, 1978: 503, part. (= *nigra* Kraatz, 1859 = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) - “Europe méridionale, Caucase”; Starzyk & Lessaer, 1978: 35-45; Holzschuh, 1981: 81, part. (“türkisch- und russisch Armenien, Kaukasus, Talysch, Elburz und Kopet Dagh”); Berger, 1985: 169-171, part. – Alpes-Maritimes and Caucasus; Tsherepanov, 1985: 209, part; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 355, part. – Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kopet-Dag, West Europe; Tsherepanov, 1985: 209, part. (= *nigra* Kr.) – Middle Europe, Caucasus, Crimea, ?South Urals; Sláma, 1998: 294, part.; Brustel, Berger & Cocquempot, 2002: 455, part. – “dans les Alpes-Maritimes et les Hautes-Alpes”, “Grèce”, “Caucase”; Bartenev, 2004: 39 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.), part. - from West Europe to Turkmenia; 2009: 339 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.), part. - from West Europe to Turkmenia; Kasatkin, 2005: 56 – Rostov Region of Russia; Özdikmen & Turgut, 2008: 623, part. (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) – “Europe (?France, ?Italy, ?Romania, ?Hungary, ?Czechia, ?Slovakia, Crimea, S European Russia), Caucasus (Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan), Central Asia (Turkmenia), Iran”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 332, part. – Azerbajdzhan, Armenia, Georgia, South Russia, Ukraine, Iran, Turkmenia; Miroshnikov, 2011: 259 – Adygeya Region; Berger, 2012: 607, part. (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) – “France, Italie, Croatei, Grèce occidentale, Turquie, Iran, Caucase”
- Tetrops praeusta* var. *gilvipes*, Bogdanov-Katkov, 1917: 51 – “Ekaterinodar”; Aurivillius, 1922: 572, - Kaukasus; Winkler, 1929: 1226, – Caucasus.
- Tetrops praeusta gilvipes*, Plavilstshikov, 1932: 195 - Caucasus; Villiers, 1967: 377, part. - “propre à la région caucasienne”, “Iran: Tariki Rud”;
- Tetrops praeusta*, Harde, 1966: 94, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.)
- Tetrops praeusta* ab *nigra*, Kaszab, 1971: 283, part.
- Tetrops praeustus*, Sama, 1988: 190, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.); Bense, 1995: 469, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.);

Type locality. Armenia – see above.

Diagnosis. Pronotum with relatively dense punctation, covered by brown erect setae; elytra always totally black with brown erect setae, densely punctated with relatively big dots; legs totally yellow; body length in males: 3.5-4.8 mm, width: 1.2-1.4 mm; body length in females: 3.7-5.3 mm, width: 1.0-1.5mm.

Distribution. South Russia: south of Rostov Region, about whole Krasnodar Region, Adygeya, south of Stavropol Region (Pyatigorsk, Praskoveya), Chechnya; Georgia (Borzhome, Mtzheta, Telavi, Mukhray) and Abkhazia (Mamzyshkha Mt.); Armenia (Sevan, Alagez); Turkey (Artvin).

Material. 1 male, Borzhomi - ZMM; 1 male, Mtzhet, E.Koenig - ZMM; 2 males, Cauc. Bor., (Cammpì), Pyatigorsk, A.Zolotarev - ZMM; 1 male, Sochi env, Koval – MD; 3 males, 1 female, Telav, 10.04.1907, 08.06.1907 -

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ZMM; 1 male, Stavropol, 7-13.05.1914, B.Zolotorevsky - ZMM; 3 males, 2 females, Kuban, Mingrelskoe, 10.04.1930, 28.04.1930, V.Galkin - ZMM; 2 males, 1 female, Maykop, 22.04.1931, 30.05.1931, Shaposhnikov - ZMM; 1 male, Maykop, 30.05.1933 – ZMM; 2 males, Maykop, 19 15/05. 1935, Shaposhnikov – MD; 1 male, Georgia, Mukhrai, 19.04.1957, D.Loosovoy - ZMM; 1 male, Guzeripl, 07.06.1970, Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Krasnodar, 03.1979, Miroshnikov – MD; 1 male, 1 female, Krasnodar reg., Khodizhensk, 15.05.1979, Miroshnikov – MD; 1 male, Krasnodar reg., Khodizhensk, 08.05.1985, Okhrimenko – MD; 1 male, Abkhazia, Mamzyshkha, 04.06.1985, Okhrimenko – MD; 1 male, Turcia, Artvin, Savsat, 1700-2000 m, 22-23.06, 1994, G.Sama – GS; 3 males, 1 female, Rostov Region, Egorlykskaya, 15.05.2003, D.Kasatkin – MD; 1 male, Krasnodar reg., Sukko, 44°46'N 37°23' E, 01.06.2010, M.Danilevsky – MD.

***Tetrops gilvipes efetovi* ssp. n.**
(Figs 1-4)

Tetrops gilvipes, Ogloblin, 1948: 471, part. – Ciscaucasia, Crimea; Plavilstshikov, 1965: 419 part. – Caucasus, Crimea; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 355, part. – Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kopet-Dag, West Europe; Tsherepanov., 1985: 209 (= *nigra* Kr.) – Middle Europe, Caucasus, Crimea, ?South Urals; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 36, part; Bartenev, 2004: 39 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.), part. - from West Europe to Turkmenia; 2009: 339 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.), part. - from West Europe to Turkmenia; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 332 – Azerbajdzhan, Armenia, Georgia, South Russia, Ukraine, Iran, Turkmenia.

Tetrops praeusta praeusta, Bartenev, 2004: 39 (= *nigra* Kr.), part. – from West Europe and North Africa to Kazakhstan; 2009: 336 (= *nigra* Kr.), part. – from West Europe and North Africa to Kazakhstan;

Type locality. Crimea, Simferopol.

Diagnosis. Pronotum moderately punctated with erect pale setae; elytra from totally yellow to totally dark-brown, often yellow with dark apex; covered by pale erect pubescence, with rather distinct punctuation; legs totally yellow; body length in males: 4.2-4.9 mm, width: 1.1-1.2 mm; body length in females: 3.9-5.1 mm, width: 1.1-1.3mm.

T. g. efetovi ssp.n. differs from Caucasian *T. g. gilvipes* by the presence of numerous specimens with yellow elytra, and from European *T. g. adlbaueri* ssp.n. by the presence of numerous specimens with dark-brown elytra. In fact *T. g. efetovi* ssp.n. is a

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transitional population between *T. g. gilvipes* and *T. g. adlbaueri* ssp.n.

Distribution. Ukraine, Crimea Peninsula.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, „Crimea, Simferopol, 30.04.1998, K.Efetov leg.“ – MD; 71 paratypes: 4 males Crimea, Alma River, Rybakov – ZIN; 4 males, 4 females, Alushta, B.V.Stark – ZMM, MD; 1 male, 1 female, Simferopol, 31.04.1908, 19.05.1908, O G.&K.Khristoforovy - ZMM; 1 male, Crimea, Artek, 20.06.1925 – ZMM; 7 males, 5 females, Simferopol, 09.04.1932 - ZMM; 1 male, Simferopol, 20. 05. 1935 – MD; 2 males, Simferopol, 19 5/06. 1935 – MD; 2 males, Saryj Krym, 27.05.1946 - ZMM; 1 male, Krym, Pionerskoe, 16.04.1975, Zhelkhovtzev - ZMM; 3 males, 1 female, Yalta, 08.06.1984, Mindal, S.Saluk – MD; 1 male, 2 females, Alushta, 28.04.1950, B.V.Stark – MD; 2 male, Chatyr Dag Mt., 1200 m, 19.05.1989, E.E.Perkovsky – MD; 1 male, Simferopol, 20.05.1991 - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Krym, Sudak distr., 2km N Veselyj, 30.04.1994, I.Melnik - MPSU; 1 male, 1 female, Krym, Sudak distr., 2km N Veselyj, 30.04.1994, Udovichenko - MPSU; 5 males, 2 females, Simferopol, 30.04.1998, K.Efetov leg. – MD; 10 males, Crimea, Andrusovo, Simferopol, 06.06.2009. A.Napolov - AN; 3 males, Crimea, Klinovka, Simferopol, 06.06.2009. A.Napolov - AN; 4 males, Crimea, Krasnolesie, Simferopol, 02.06.2009, 04.06.2009, A.Napolov – AN.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to Konstantin Efetov – a well known specialist on world Zigaenidae (Lepidoptera), who collected the holotype and a part of the type series.

***Tetrops gilvipes murzini* ssp. n.**
(Figs 5-6)

Tetrops gilvipes, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 200, part. - North Armenia, Sevan, Alagez; 1955: 546, part. - Caucasus, Transcaucasus, Turcmenia (Kopet-Dag); Murzin, 1977: 302, part. - Caucasus, Kopetdag; Holzschuh, 1981: 81, part. (“türkisch- und russisch Armenien, Kaukasus, Talysch, Elburz und Kopet Dagh”); Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 355, part. – Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kopet-Dag, West Europe; Bartenev, 2004: 39 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.), part. - from West Europe to Turkmenia; 2009: 339 (= *muehlfeldi* Muls.), part. - from West Europe to Turkmenia; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 332 – Azerbajdzhan, Armenia, Georgia, South Russia, Ukraine, Iran, Turkmenia; Berger, 2012: 607 part. (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.)– “France, Italie, Croatei, Grèce occidentale, Turquie, Iran, Caucase”.

Tetrops praeusta gilvipes, Villiers, 1967: 377, part. (“propre à la région caucasienne”, “Iran: Tariki Rud”);

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Type locality. West Turkmenia, Kopetdag, Ay-Dere.

Diagnosis. Pronotum sparsely punctated and sparsely setose; pronotal middle about glabrous with scattered pale erect setae; elytra always black with pale erect setae; elytra with strong big punctation; legs totally yellow; body length in males: 3.0-4.7 mm, width: 0.9-1.4 mm; body length in females: 4.1-5.8 mm, width: 1.4-1.6 mm.

Distribution. South-West Turkmenia, Kopetdag (Ay-Dere, Pir-Dare, Kara-Kala); South-East Azerbajdzhan, Talysh area (Gasmalyan, Lerik, Shovu); North Iran (Villiers, 1967: “Tariki Rud” – Mazandaran near Caspian Sea; Holzschuh, 1981: Nord Iran, Elburz: Gilan, Mazandaran).

Material. Holotype, 1 male, „W. Kopet Dag, Ay Dere, Grusha, 25.11.1985, S.Murzin“ – ML; Paratypes: 1 male, Caspi.M.Gebiet, Liryk, Leder Reitter – ZMM; 1 male, Kopet-Dag, Pir-Dare, 08.05.1930, Shestoperov - ZMM; 1 males, Lerik, 21.05.1971, M.Badalov – MD; 1 male, Kopet-Dag, Ay-Dere, 19.04.1975, Yanushev – MD; 6 males, 1 females, Talysh, Gasmalyan, 28.05-07.06.1980, V.Belov – MD; 53 males, 64 female Kopet-Dag, Ay-Dere, 25.11.1985, .12.1985, 01.12.1985, 11.12.1985 S.Murzin – ZIN, SM, ML; 1 male, 1 female, Talysh, Shovu, 11.05.1986, S.Saluk – SM; 2 males, Kopet-Dag, Garygala, 05.1994, J.Myatlenski – MD; 1 female, Kopet-Dag, Kara-Kala, Bogandar, 22.04.1992, V.Grachev – MD.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to my friend Sergey Murzin – a well known specialist on Cerambycidae, who collected the holotype and a part of the type series.

***Tetrops gilvipes adlbaueri* ssp. n.**
(Figs 7-8)

Tetrops “A”, Švácha, 2001: 293 – West Europe.

Type locality. Bohemia, Závist.

Diagnosis. Pronotum sparsely punctated and sparsely setose; pronotal middle about glabrous with scattered brown erect setae; elytra always yellow with dark apex; strongly punctated, with brown erect setae; legs yellow with more or less darkened middle and hind femora; body length: 4.4-4.6 mm, width: 1.1-1.2 mm.

The base for the separation of the new taxon was the larval structure of so called “*Tetrops* A” (Švácha, 2001) from West Europe, which is just the same as in *T. gilvipes* from Caucasus (Danilevsky &

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Miroshnikov, 1985) - fine and dense spiculae covering abdominal segments. Imagoes of “*Tetrops A*” are similar externally to *T. praeusta* and could be distinguished by male genitalia only. The type series of males of *T. g. adlbaueri* was received from P.Švácha as presumably received from the larvae of “*T. gilvipes*” – type. The study of genitalia of several specimens from that series shows that it really belongs to *T. gilvipes*.

The problem of the real nature of the type of *T. praeusta* (L.) rests open, but most probably it belongs to *Tetrops* “B” sensu Švácha (2001), as much more numerous species in Europe.

Distribution. Most probably the taxon is distributed all over area of European *T. praeusta*.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, „Bohemia, Za'vist, 21.5.72, Dr. V. Seichert“ – MD; Paratypes: 1 male, 1 female, Bohemia, Za'vist, 21.05.1972, Dr. V. Seichert – MD.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to Karl Adlbauer - the famous European Cerambycidae specialist.

***Tetrops gilvipes niger* Kraatz, 1859.**

Tetrops nigra Kraatz, 1859: 57 - „Sardinien“; Holzschuh, 1981: 82, part.; Sláma, 1998: 293, part.;

Polyopsia gilvipes, Mulsant, 1862: 347 (+ var. *nigra* Kr.) – “le Caucase, etc.”.

Polyopsia gilvipes var. *muehlfeldi* Mulsant, 1862: 348 – “dans les Alpes cottiennes”

Tetrops gilvipes, Breuning, 1965: 651 (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) – “S. Germany, Austria”); Villiers, 1978: 503, part. (= *nigra* Kraatz, 1859 = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) - “Europe méridionale, Caucase”; Berger, 1985: 169-171, part. – Alpes-Maritimes and Caucasus; Tsherepanov, 1985: 209 (= *nigra* Kr.) – Middle Europe, Caucasus, Crimea, ?South Urals; Brustel, Berger & Cocquemot, 2002: 455 – “dans les Alpes-Maritimes et les Hautes-Alpes”, “Grèce”, “Caucase”; Berger, 2012: 607 part. (= *nigra* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) – “France, Italie, Croatie, Grèce occidentale, Turquie, Iran, Caucase”

Tetrops praeusta var. *nigra*, Ganglbauer 1882: 586, part.; Aurivillius, 1922: 573, part. – Gebirgsgegenden Süddeutschlands, Alpen; Planet, 1924: 327, part.; Winkler, 1929: 1226 – Alpes;

Tetrops praeusta ab *nigra*, Kaszab, 1971: 283, part.

Tetrops praeustus, Sama, 1988: 190, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.); 2002: 120, part. (= *nigra* Kr.); Bense, 1995: 469, part. (= *gilvipes* Fald. = *nigra* Kr.); Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 36, part. (= *nigra* Kr.); Sláma, 2006: 38, part. (= *nigra* Kr.)

Tetrops niger, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1994: 58., part.

Tetrops praeusta praeusta, Bartenev, 2004: 39 (= *nigra* Kr.), part. – from West

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Europe and North Africa to Kazakhstan; 2009: 336 (= *nigra* Kr.), part. – from West Europe and North Africa to Kazakhstan;

Tetrops praeustus praeustus, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 333, part. (= *niger* Kr. = *muehlfeldi* Muls.) Europe, Turkey, Syria, Transcaucasus, West and East Siberia, Kazakhstan, Mongolia; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 146, part. – Italy.

Type locality. Italy, Piedmont.

According to Sama (1988) the record of Sardinia in the original description was wrong and the real type locality is “Piedmont, Italy”.

Diagnosis. Pronotum with moderately sparse punctation with numerous pale erect setae; elytra usually dark-brown or nearly black with relatively big punctation and pale erect setae; legs are always yellow; sometimes elytra could be yellow similar to *T. praeusta*, according to a single available male from Susa with totally yellow legs and yellow elytra, but with short and wide parameres typical for *T. gilvipes*; genital structure in males of *T. gilvipes niger* is very similar to genitals of males of other subspecies; body length in males: 4.6-4.7 mm, width: 1.1-1.2 mm; body length in a female: 4.6-4.8 mm, width: 1.2-1.4 mm.

Remark. The analyses of male genitaliae of black specimens with yellow legs from Italy and France shows that they belong to *T. gilvipes*.

A rather special opinion was formulated by G.Sama (2002): “In conclusion, *T.nigra* seems to be a transitional form between *T.praeustus* and *T.gilvipes*”.

Distribution. North Western Italy, South-East France and Switzerland.

Material. 5 male, Fontanigorda, chapelle 22.05.1988, M.Magistretti – GS; 2 female, Grondola, 22.05.1988, P. Berger – GS. 1 male, Piemonte-Susa, 17.04.1976, R.Hourulia – MD.

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REFERENCES

- Althoff J., Danilevsky M.L., 1997. A check-list of Longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycoidea) of Europe. Slovensko Entomolosko Društvo Stefana Michielijja. Ljubljana. 64pp.
- Aurivillius C. 1922. Cerambycidae: Lamiinae I. Pars 73. In: Schenkling S. (ed.). Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen XXIII. Cerambycidae II. Berlin: W. Junk, pp. 1-322.
- Bartenev A.F., 2009. [Longicorn-beetles of Left-Bank Ukraine and Crimea. Kharkov: Kharkov National University], 405pp. [in Russian]
- Bartenev A.F., 2004. A review of the long-horned beetles species (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the fauna of Ukraine.- Izvestiya Kharkovskogo Entomologicheskogo Obshestva [The Kharkov Entomological Society Gazette], 2003(2004), 11(1-2): 24-43. [in Russian]
- Bense U. 1995. Longhorn Beetles. Illustrated Key to the Cerambycidae and Vesperidae of Europe. Margrat Werlag, Weikersheim. 512 pp.
- Berger P., 1985. Note sur le genre *Tetrops* (Col., Cerambycidae).- L'Entomologiste, 41(4): 169-172.
- Berger P. 2000. Contribution à la connaissance de la faune de Grèce: (Coleoptera : Cerambycidae), 2e note. – Biocosme mésogéen, 16 [1999]: 101-106.
- Berger P. 2012. Coléoptères Cerambycidae de la faune de France Continentale et de Corse. Actualisation de l'ouvrage d'André Villiers, 1978. Supplément au Tome XXI R.A.R.E.: 664pp.
- Bogdanov-Katkov N.N., 1917. [To the fauna of Longicorn-beetles of Kuban Region.- Archives of Caucasian Museum], 11: 33-53. [in Russian]
- Breuning S. 1965. Catalogue des Lamiaires du Monde (Col.,Ceramby.). 8. Lief. Im Verlag des Museums G. Frey. Munchen: 559-655.
- Brustel H., Berger P. & Cocquemot Ch., 2002. Catalogue des Vesperidae et des Cerambycidae de la faune de France (Coleoptera).- Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (n.s.), 2002, 38 (4): 443-461.
- Cocquemot Ch., 1992. Réhabilitation de la présence en France de *Tetrops starki* Chevrolat (Col. Cerambycidae). L'Entomologiste, 48(4): 201-202.
- Danilevsky M.L., Miroschnikov A.I., 1985. [Timber-Beetles of Caucasus (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)]. Krasnodar: 419 pp. [in Russian]
- Faldennann F. 1837. Fauna entomologica transcaucasica. Coleoptera II. Nouvelles Memoires de la Societe des Natlralistes de Moscou 5: 1-433, 15 pis. [separate issue: Fauna entomologica Trans-Callcasica. Coleoptera. Pars 2. Moscou: l'imprimerie d'Auguste Semen, Imprimeur de l' Academie Imperiale Medico-Chirurgicale, 433 pp., pl. 1-15].
- Ganglbauer L., 1882a. Beiträge zur Synonymik der europäischen und caucasischen Cerambyciden. Wiener Entomologische Zeitung I. Heft 1. 5-12.
- Ganglbauer L. 1882b. Bestimmungstabellen der europäischen Coleopteren. VII. Cerambycidae. Verhandlungen der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien, 31 [1881]: 681-758, pl. 22.
- Harde V. 1966. 87. Familie: Cerambycidae, Bockkäfer, S. 7-94. In: Freude H., Harde K. W. & Lohse G.A. Die Käfer Mitteleuropas. Bd. 9. Krefeld:

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- Goecke & Evers: 299 S.
- Heyrovský L. 1955. Fauna ČSR, Svazek 5. Tesaříkovití- Cerambycidae. (Řád brouci – Coleoptera).- Praha: Nakladatelství Československé Akademie Věd: 346 + [1] pp.
- Holzschuh C., 1981. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der europaischen Tetrots-Arten (Cerambycidae, Col.).- Koleopterologische Rundschau, 55: 77-89.
- Kasatkin D.G., Arzanov Ju.G. 1997. [Der Bockkaffer (Cerambycidae). Material für fauna der Kaffer (Coleoptera) norden Kaukasus und untere Don.]- Records of Kharkov Entomological Society, 5, 2: 63-70. [in Russian]
- Kasatkin D.G., 2005. The new data on the longicorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) south of Russia and conjoint territories.- Caucasian Entomological Bulletin, v.1(1): 55-56. [in Russian]
- Kaszab Z., 1971. Cincérek-Cerambycidae.- Fauna Hungariae, Bd. 106. Budapest: 1-283, 1-17.
- Löbl I. & Smetana A. (ed.), 2010. Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Vol. 6. Chrysomeloidea. Stenstrup: Apollo Books. 924 pp.
- Miroshnikov A.I. 2011. [Family Cerambycidae – Longhorn-beetles, Timber-beetle. (pp. 239-263). In: Zamotajlov A.S. & Nikitsky N.B. (red.) Coleopterous Insects (Insecta, Coleoptera) of Republic of Adygheya (annotated catalogue of species) (Fauna conspecta of Adygheya. N1). Maykop: Adyghei State University Publishers] (2010): 404. [In Russian]
- Mulsant E., 1862. Longicornes [Pp. 1-480]. In: Histoire naturelle des coléoptères de France. Ed. 2. Paris: Magnin, Blanchard et Cie, successeurs de Louis Janet, 590 pp.
- Murzin S.V. 1977. A new species of the genus *Tetrots* (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Mongolia.- Insects of Mongolia, vol. 5, Leningrad, “Nauka”: 301-303.
- Ogloblin D.A., 1948. 73. Fam. Cerambycidae – Timber Beetles or Longhorned Beetles. In: A Key of the Insects of the European Part of the USSR. Moscow-Leningrad]: 450-471 [in Russian]
- Özdikmen, H. & Turgut, S. 2008. The genus *Tetrots* Stephens, 1829 with a new subspecies, *Tetrots praeustus anatolicus* ssp. n. from Turkey (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiinae). *Munis Entomology & Zoology* 3 (2): 621-635
- Pesarini C., Sabbadini A., 1994. Insetti della Fauna Europea. Coleotteri Cerambicidi.- *Natura. Rivista di Scienze Naturali*, vol. 85, fasc. 1/2: 132pp.
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1932. [Timber Beetles - Wood Pests]. Moscow, Leningrad: 200 pp. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1948. [A Key for Longicorn Beetles of Armenia.] Erevan: 232 pp. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1955. 15. Fam. Cerambycidae – timber beetles, longicorn beetles.- In: Pests of forest. Moscow-Leningrad: 493-546. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1965. 75-th Fam. Cerambycidae - Timber Beetles, Longicornes.- In: A Key to Insects of the European Part of the USSR, v. 2, Coleoptera and Strepsiptera. Moscow-Leningrad, “Nauka”: 389-419.
- Sama G. 1988. Coleoptera. Cerambycidae. Catalogo topographico e sinonimico. Fauna d'Italia, vol. 25, 216 pp.
- Sama G., 2002. Atlas of the Cerambycidae of Europe and the Mediterranean Area.

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Vol.1. Nakladatelství Kabourek. Zlín: 173 pp.

- Schmidt G. 1958. Untersuchungen über die mitteleuropäischen Vertreter des Genus *Tetrops* Stephens (Col. Cerambycidae) (6. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der paläarktischen Cerambycidae) – Mitteilungen der Deutschen Entomologischen Gesellschaft. Heft 3: 53-60.
- Sláma M., 1998. Tesaříkovití – Cerambycidae České republiky a Slovenské republiky (Brouci – Coleoptera). Praha: 383pp
- Sláma M., 2006. Coleoptera: Cerambycidae.- Folia Heyrovskyana Serie B, Icones Insectorum Europae Centralis. 2006 June 20; 4: 1-40.
- Starzyk J.R. & Lessaer M., 1978. Studies on the distribution, morphology and biology of *Tetrops starki* Chev., (Col., Cerambycidae). Zeitschrift für angewandte Entomologie, Bd.86, H.1: 35-46.
- Švácha P. 2001. 17. Überfamilie: Chrysomeloidea. 114. Familie: Cerambycidae, Lamiinae. In: Klauzntzer B. Die Larven der Käfer Mitteleuropas, Bd. 6. Polyphaga. Teil 5. Berlin: 248-298.
- Tsherepanov A.I. 1985. [Longicorn Beetles of North Asia (Lamiinae: Saperdini - Tetraopini). Novosibirsk: 256pp.] [in Russian]
- Villiers A. 1967. Contribution à la faune de l'Iran. I: Coléoptères Cerambycidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (N. S.) **3**: 327-379.
- Villiers A. 1978. Faune des coléoptères de France I. Cerambycidae. Encyclopédie Entomologique XLII. Paris: Editions Lechevalier, xxvii + 611 pp.

INSCRIPTION FOR FIGURES

Figs 1-4. *Tetrops gilvipes efetovi* **ssp. n.:** 1 – Holotypus, male, Simferopol 30.4.1998 – MD; 2 - female, Simferopol 30.4.1998 – MD; 3 - male, Yalta, 8.6.84, mindal, S.Saluk – MD; 4 – females, Yalta, mindal, 08.06.1984, S.Soluk - MD

Figs 5-6. *Tetrops gilvipes murzini* **ssp. n.:** 5 – Holotypus, male, W Kopetdag, Ay-Dere, Grusha, 25.11.1985 S.Murzin – ML; 6 - Paratypus, female, W Kopetdag, Ay-Dere, Mindal, 01.12.1985 S.Murzin – ML

Figs 7-8. *Tetrops gilvipes adlbaueri* **ssp. n.:** 7-8 – Bohemia, Za'vist, 21.05.1972, Dr. V. Seichert (7 - Holotype, male – MD; 8 - Paratype, female – MD)

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